

Soft Computing Methods for Predicting Environmental Quality: A Case Study of the Zimbabwe Sugar Processing Industry

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Sugarcane growing and processing is associated with environmental degradation and pollution. The impact that sugar processing industries have on the environment affects the ecosystem. Methods of soft computing that is fuzzy logic, neural networks, and genetic algorithms can be adopted for environmental protection, particularly in the developing countries. Soft computing techniques, particularly neural networks and fuzzy logic, have been used to predict and sometimes control air quality. This paper looks at how fuzzy logic can be adopted for predicting air quality. The common environmental impacts associated with sugarcane production are water and air pollution. This paper focuses on air pollution. The major waste streams are identified and the extent of air pollution is predicted by classifying the air quality as poor, ordinary, very good, and excellent. This paper presents a fuzzy rule base that can be used to classify the pollutants and predict the air quality based on the amount of the specific pollutant in the air. The Mamdani fuzzy inference system is used to build the rule base, with the membership functions being non-intersecting and triangular. The adoption of fuzzy logic techniques will help sugar processing industries to be aware of the impact their operations have on the environment.

Keywords: environmental protection, pollution, soft computing, fuzzy logic

Sugarcane growing in Zimbabwe has numerous negative impacts on the environment. Coupled with the local impacts is the pressure being exerted by the international community to improve environmental performance, where organizations are expected to gear toward greener production or engage in environmental best practices that ensure waste minimization at every stage of production. The environmental pressures associated with the production of sugarcane in Zimbabwe are similar to those of other sugar industries around the world. For this reason, perceptions regarding the negative environmental impacts of cane production are also similar all over the world. This paper looks at how soft computing methods of fuzzy logic can be adopted for air quality prediction in the Zimbabwe sugar processing industry. The common environmental impacts associated with sugarcane production are water and air pollution. In this paper, the major waste streams are identified as well as the strategic locations of the equipment for measuring and/or controlling pollution. This

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paper presents interventions for real time monitoring (with the aid of Real World Computing) on waste generation and predicts the quality of the atmosphere in order to warn operations and engineering departments on the necessary measures needed to maintain a clean atmospheric environment. The research outlines how electronic equipment and soft computing, particularly fuzzy logic, can be used to classify and quantify levels of pollution in sugarcane processing. The study also aims at coming up with recommendations for proper methods for segregation, collection, transportation, treatment and disposal of the different forms of generated waste.

Sugarcane Growing and Processing Overview

Sugarcane processing is focused on the production of cane sugar (sucrose) from sugarcane. Other products of the processing include bagasse, molasses, and filter-cake. Bagasse, the residual woody fibre of the cane, is used for several purposes: fuel for the boilers and lime kilns, production of numerous paper and paperboard products and reconstituted panel board, agricultural mulch, and as a raw material for production of chemicals.

Impacts of the Sugarcane Industry on the Environment

Some of the environmental pollution associated with sugarcane growing and processing are:

- (1) Water pollution;
- (2) Air pollution;
- (3) Noise;
- (4) Bad odours (stench due to by products such as molasses);
- (5) Land pollution (spillages and stillage);
- (6) Soil degradation;
- (7) Biodiversity threats.

The following sections discuss water and air pollution further.

Water pollution. Discharge from the mill (the caustic soda, soap, and greases and oils from mill equipment wash waters) is the major contributor to water pollution in sugarcane growing and processing industries. High levels of pollutants in river water systems cause an increase in biological oxygen demand (BOD), chemical oxygen demand (COD), total dissolved solids (TDS), total suspended solids (TSS), and toxic metals such as Cd, Cr, Ni, and Pb, and hence make such water unsuitable for drinking, irrigation and aquatic life (Kanu & Achi, 2011). Herbicides and pesticides regularly have an impact beyond their specific intended target, and affect indigenous plant and animal life (Hay, 2000).

Air pollution. Boiler performance and furnace emissions such as carbon monoxide (CO), nitrogen oxides (NO_x), sulphur oxides (SO_x), unburnt fuel and particulates are of considerable concern to the sugar industry (Rainey, Pennisi, & Joyce, 2004). Sugarcane plantations take advantage of bagasse for use as a boiler fuel. Bagasse is the crushed remaining of sugarcane stalks left after the extraction of juice (Janghathaikul & Gheewala, 2004). Bagasse is normally supplemented with coal for start-up firing. Most of the gaseous emissions are not visible to the naked eye. Particulates (soot) are also released into the atmosphere during steam generation as shown in Figure 1.

In sugarcane plantations, the major areas that contribute to air pollution are cane burning, steam generation and waste incineration. Cane burning (see Figure 2) is a nuisance, it is potentially hazardous, and it impacts negatively on surrounding communities (Hay, 2000).

Vehicle movement to and from the milling points in sugar milling companies is another source of air

pollution through exhaust fumes and dust. Often the growing of sugarcane may require clearing of fields using graders and tractors for tilling the land. During dry periods of the year, these operations lead to significant air pollution (dust). A land clearing operation is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 1. Air pollution due to boiler stack emissions.

Figure 2. Cane burning.

Figure 3. Land and bush clearing operation.

Local legislative Regulations

Various legislative Acts issued through Environmental Management Agency (EMA) recognize sugarcane cultivation as a specific activity that impacts on the environment. This relates particularly to soil and water conservation, atmospheric pollution and practices that might affect the health and safety of labourers. EMA, through the Act, enforces that polluters should “pay to pollute” (Atmospheric Pollution Control Regulations SI 72 of 2009) (Parliament of Zimbabwe, 2000).

For any other sources of pollution, companies can apply for separate licences to pollute to a specific level (that is, a particular band). Table 1 presents “pay to pollute” bands.

Table 1

“Pay to Pollute” Bands

Pollutant	Blue band	Green band	Yellow band	Red band
Particulates (mg/m ³)	< 60	< 90	< 100	< 120
SO ₂ (mg/m ³)	< 30	< 40	< 45	< 50
NO ₂ (mg/m ³)	< 70	< 100	< 130	< 150

External Environmental Issues

International and local environmental pressures recognized as being of the greatest concern in the Zimbabwean sugar industry have been identified, mainly through comments made by outside parties, local community leadership and extension staff within the industry, coupled to the formal environmental audit of the industry as a whole, that is at the ISO 14001 certification level but in the offing has taken place. The general consensus appears to be that environmental standards within the industry are improving, but at a very slow pace. However, there are a few grower groups in the industry that are leading the way with regard to environmental management.

Environmental legislation around the world is developing fast, and is focusing on international conventions and legislation (a case in particular being the Agenda 21) that encompass all aspects of growing, producing and selling the product. The world's most popular definition of sustainable development is "development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the needs of future generations to meet their own needs". Concern for the environment is growing internationally and is affecting the way business is carried out, on the local stage here in Zimbabwe, since we are also part of the global community. There is international consensus to implement principles and rules that halt degradation of the environment and encourage conservation of existing natural resources. Pressure to enforce environmental legislation is growing, with international focus regarding environmental issues being on: air pollution (cane burning), genetically modified organisms, labour issues, fresh water use and contamination, and soil degradation.

Soft Computing Techniques in Prediction Problems

Prediction based on traditional mathematical methods is often found wanting in dealing with non-linear and uncertain systems. Hence, some other replacements such as soft computing methods have been proposed with different advantages and disadvantages. Soft computing has three ranches: artificial neural networks, fuzzy logic and genetic algorithms. Previously air quality has been predicted using machine learning models such as decision trees, neural networks and decision trees (Deleawe, Kusznir, Lamb, & Cook, 2010). It is evident that soft computing techniques are moving forward as an impending tool to model a highly intricate system like atmosphere. The atmosphere is a highly complex, dynamic and non-linear system. Soft computing methods are well adapted to solving such systems and fuzzy logic in particular can be applied because of its ability to handle the various linguistic variables associated with environmental quality.

Fuzzy Logic

A fuzzy controller is an artificial decision maker that operates in a closed-loop system in real time. It gathers plant output data $y(t)$, compares it to the reference input $r(t)$, and then decides what the plant input $u(t)$ should be to ensure that the performance objectives are met (Craig, 2011). In fuzzy rule based systems, after modelling, knowledge is presented by If-Then rules. Fuzzy rules consist of two parts: an antecedent part stating conditions on the input variable(s), and a consequent part describing the corresponding values of the output variable(s). Given particularly values of the input variables, the degree of fulfillment of each rule is obtained by aggregating the membership degrees of these input values into the respective fuzzy sets (Gallego, Gago, & Landín, 2011). A fuzzy controller can include empirical rules, and that is especially useful in operator controlled plants (Jantzen, 1998).

According to Bevrani (2010), a fuzzy rule can be defined as a conditional statement in the form:

$$\text{If } x \text{ is } A, \text{ then } y \text{ is } B \quad (1)$$

Where x and y are linguistic variables; and A and B are linguistic values determined by fuzzy sets on the universe of discourses X and Y , respectively (Bevrani, 2010). The rule-base holds the knowledge, in the form of a set of rules, of how best to control the system.

Methodology and Results

The major pollutant generators were identified (boilers and incinerators) and focus of sampling and measurement were directed to these. Air quality was assessed and the major findings are presented in Tables 2-6. The equipment used to measure emissions includes online opacimeters and portable automated

ECOM.J2KN flue gas analysers. For each pollutant four samples were taken at each of the identified generators. The results presented in the summary of findings show the averaged air pollution level.

Summary of Findings

The summary of measurement results on CO, SO₂, NO₂, and particulates is presented in this section (see Tables 2-6).

CO levels shown in Table 1 and Figure 4 are way above that for world class performers (normally less than 0.1 ppm). Fuel type and boiler firing practices that lead to incomplete combustion are the main causes of high CO levels.

Table 2

CO Emissions (ppm)

Plant	Actual	Local implication
Boiler 1	160	Not specified
Boiler 2	48	Not specified
Boiler 3	231	Not specified
Boiler 4	478	Not specified
Incinerator 1	14	Not specified
Incinerator 2	14	Not specified

Figure 4. CO emissions (ppm).

Table 3

SO₂ (mg/m³)

Plant	Actual	Local implication
Boiler 1	0	Blue
Boiler 2	0	Blue
Boiler 3	0	Blue
Boiler 4	0	Blue
Incinerator 1	13	Blue
Incinerator 2	15	Blue

Figure 5. SO₂ emissions (mg/m³).

Table 4

NO₂ (mg/m³)

Plant	Actual	Local implication
Boiler 1	27	Blue
Boiler 2	41	Green
Boiler 3	25	Blue
Boiler 4	33	Blue
Incinerator 1	20	Blue
Incinerator 2	5	Blue

Figure 6. NO₂ emissions (mg/m³).

Table 5

 NO_x (mg/m^3)

Plant	Actual	Local implication
Boiler 1	127	Not specified
Boiler 2	95	Not specified
Boiler 3	79	Not specified
Boiler 4	103	Not specified
Incinerator 1	57	Not specified
Incinerator 2	13	Not specified

Figure 7. NO_x emissions (mg/m^3).

For the results in Tables 3-5 and Figures 5-7, it can be seen that the NO_x and SO_x emissions for the study are quite high by national and international standards (although these emissions are within the national “blue” range). Good boiler firing (fuel type, fuel chemical specifications, combustion characteristics, and air/fuel ratios) practices can be adopted to reduce these emissions.

From the data in Table 6 and Figure 8, it can be seen that the emission levels are high, especially when compared against international standards. The “yellow” range indicates performing way outside Zimbabwean standards. Particulates can be reduced by use of cyclones and wet scrubbers among other pollution control technologies. Operations such as land and bush clearing also contribute to high levels of particulates. Such operations should be carried out during the wet season wherever possible to reduce dust generation.

Table 6

Particulates (mg/m^3)

Plant	Actual	Local implication
Boiler 1	97	Yellow
Boiler 2	52	Blue
Boiler 3	65	Green
Boiler 4	41	Blue
Incinerator 1	14	Blue
Incinerator 2	10	Blue

Figure 8. Particulates emission (mg/m³).

Summary of Fuzzy Rule Development for Approximating Air Quality

A set of fuzzy rules was developed using the Mamdani type fuzzy inference system to approximate the ambient air quality. Air quality is categorised into poor, ordinary, very good, and excellent. The technical interventions at each stage will be based on the actual air quality level and these quality levels can be used to inform management or operatives on the required technical interventions. The interventions can then be implemented manually or automatically. The idea is that air quality should be excellent and therefore all technical efforts should result in continuously improving the quality of air from poor to ordinary and eventually to excellent. The developed rules are applied to all the plants and each plant is presented with an independent set of rules. The air quality is measured around specific plant locations using online/offline opacimeters and portable automated ECOM.J2KN flue gas analysers. NO₂ and NO_x emissions have been combined in building the fuzzy rule base:

- (1) If CO is high, SO₂ is high, NO_x is high, or particulates are high, then air quality is poor;
- (2) If CO is low, SO₂ is low, NO_x is low, and particulates are low, then air quality is excellent;
- (3) If CO is moderate, SO₂ is moderate, NO_x is moderate, and particulates are moderate, then air quality is ordinary;
- (4) If CO is moderate, SO₂ is low, NO_x is low, and particulates are low, then air quality is very good;
- (5) If CO is low, SO₂ is moderate, NO_x is low, and particulates are low, then air quality is very good;
- (6) If CO is low, SO₂ is low, NO_x is moderate, and particulates are low, then air quality is very good;
- (7) If CO is low, SO₂ is low, NO_x is low, and particulates are moderate, then air quality is very good;
- (8) If CO is moderate, SO₂ is moderate, NO_x is low, and particulates are moderate, then air quality is ordinary;
- (9) If CO is moderate, SO₂ is low, NO_x is moderate, and particulates are moderate, then air quality is ordinary;
- (10) If CO is low, SO₂ is moderate, NO_x is moderate, and particulates are moderate, then air quality is ordinary;

(11) If CO is moderate, SO₂ is moderate, NO_x is moderate, and particulates are low, then air quality is ordinary;

(12) If CO is moderate, SO₂ is moderate, NO_x is low, and particulates are low, then air quality is ordinary;

(13) If CO is low, SO₂ is low, NO_x is moderate, and particulates are moderate, then air quality is ordinary;

(14) If CO is moderate, SO₂ is low, NO_x is moderate, and particulates are low, then air quality is ordinary;

(15) If CO is moderate, SO₂ is low, NO_x is low, and particulates are moderate, then air quality is ordinary;

(16) If CO is low, SO₂ is moderate, NO_x is low, and particulates are moderate, then air quality is ordinary;

(17) If CO is low, SO₂ is moderate, NO_x is moderate, and particulates are low, then air quality is ordinary.

The illustration in Figure 9 is a schematic of the deduction process.

Figure 9. The air quality approximation process.

Input Membership Functions

The inputs shown in Table 7 each have three membership functions. Triangular membership functions were selected for their simplicity. The input membership functions developed are non-intersecting. For purposes of developing accommodative membership functions, the extreme high values of the inputs are deliberately higher than the actual recorded extremes in section 4. The parameters of the triangular membership function (a, b, c) are the lowest values (a) and highest values (b and c), so that the formed triangle is a right angled triangle.

Table 7

Inputs Into the Fuzzy System

Parameter	Low	Moderate	High
NO _x (mg/m ³)	0-45	45-100	100-160
Particulates (mg/m ³)	0-40	40-90	90-150
CO (ppm)	0-10	10-25	25-500
SO ₂ (mg/m ³)	0-10	10-25	25-50

Output Membership Functions

The output of the system is “air quality” to which arbitrary classification values are given as shown in Table 8. The membership functions for the outputs are triangular and non-intersecting. Again, the parameters of the triangular membership function (a, b, c) are the lowest values (a) and highest values (b and c) for each linguistic variable, so that the formed triangle is a right angled triangle.

Table 8

Output of the Fuzzy System

Parameter	Poor	Ordinary	Very good	Excellent
Air quality	1-2	2-4	4-6	6-8

Behaviour of the Air Quality Prediction System

In Figure 10, a rule viewer is presented which shows how the air quality will vary with the inputs fed into the rule base. In this instance, the air quality stands at 5.1 (that is, very good) when the inputs are NO_x : 7.36, Particulates: 19, CO: 17, and SO_2 : 3.59 as shown in the rule viewer in Figure 10.

Figure 10. Rule viewer for predicting air quality.

Generally speaking, the air quality will decrease with an increase at the levels of any of the four inputs (NO_x , Particulates, CO, and SO_2). This is illustrated in Figure 11 (for variation of air quality with NO_x), Figure 12 (for variation of air quality with SO_2) and Figure 13 (for variation of air quality with CO).

Figure 11. Variation of air quality with NO_x .

Figure 12. Variation of air quality with SO_2 .

Figure 13. Variation of air quality with CO .

Recommendations

Some recommendations are as follows:

(1) Land and bush clearing operations should be done during the wet (rain) season to minimize generation of dust during such operations;

(2) Stack emissions monitoring should be conducted on a daily basis, and not every three months as required by Environmental Management (Atmospheric Pollution Control) Regulations SI72 of 2009. Inline monitoring equipment such as opacimeters should be installed so that all technical interventions needed are implemented in time;

(3) The emission rate can be reduced by good firing characteristics (feed rate per furnace volume, excess air, reinjection of fly ash), good operating techniques, and proper equipment maintenance;

(4) The Zimbabwe sugar industry needs to embark on a strategy that will promote positive environmental trends in sugarcane and sugar production. The strategy should include the development of environmental expertise within the industry and the development and implementation of an internationally recognized environment management system for sugarcane growing and processing.

Conclusions

The paper presented a fuzzy-based approximation for air quality and discussed the way forward for the Zimbabwe sugarcane growing and processing industry. Further areas of improvement that are based on soft computing are to provide automatic technical intervention once environmental quality levels have been approximated. The Zimbabwe sugar industry's existence depends on nature running smoothly. When managed properly, sugarcane is an environmentally friendly crop in numerous ways. It is essential that the Zimbabwean sugar industry takes note of current developments that are taking place globally in other industries, so that it may start implementing these environmental awareness farming challenges now.

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